

HEART DISEASES AND STAGES OF THEIR TREATMENT

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Abstract

Cardiovascular diseases are one of the leading causes of disability and death worldwide. Early diagnosis, risk factor control, and modern treatment methods can improve the quality of life and life expectancy of patients. This article describes the most common heart diseases and the stages of their treatment.

Key words: Severe chest pain, rapid fatigue, history taking, physical examination, electrocardiography (ECG), echocardiography, blood tests, holter monitoring.

Major heart diseases

1. Ischemic heart disease (IHD)

Coronary Artery Disease develops as a result of narrowing or blockage of the coronary arteries that supply blood to the heart muscle.

Signs:

- Chest pain (angina);
- Shortness of breath;
- Rapid fatigue;
- Heart rhythm disorder.

2. Myocardial infarction

Myocardial infarction occurs when a coronary artery becomes completely blocked, resulting in necrosis of heart muscle cells.

Symptoms:

- Severe chest pain;
- Cold sweat;

- Shortness of breath;
- A feeling of fear.

3. Arterial hypertension

Hypertension is characterized by persistently high blood pressure.

Complications:

- Stroke;
- Heart failure;
- Kidney damage.

4. Heart failure

Heart Failure is a condition in which the heart is unable to pump blood to meet the body's needs.

Signs:

- Shortness of breath;
- Swelling in the legs;
- Weakness;
- Fatigue quickly.

5. Arrhythmias

Cardiac Arrhythmia — heart rhythm disorder.

Types:

- Bradycardia;
- Tachycardia;
- Atrial fibrillation;
- Ventricular arrhythmia.

Treatment steps

I stage. Diagnosis

4

The following checks are carried out:

- Anamnesis collection;
- Physical examination;
- Electrocardiography (ECG);
- Echocardiography;
- Blood tests;
- Holter monitoring;
- Coronary angiography.

Stage II. Drug treatment

Antithrombotic drugs

- Aspirin
- Clopidogrel

Hypotensive drugs

- APF inhibitors;
- Beta blockers;
- Calcium channel blockers.

Lipid-lowering agents

- Atorvastatin
- Rosuvastatin

For heart failure

- Diuretics;
- APF inhibitors;
- Beta blockers.

III stage. Interventional treatment

Percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI)

- Expansion of the coronary artery;
- Stent placement.

Coronary Bypass Surgery (CABG)

- Creating a new path for blood flow;
- It is used in multi-vessel lesions.

IV stage. Rehabilitation

Changing lifestyle

Nutrition

- Reduce salt;
- Growing vegetables and fruits;
- Limit animal fats.

Physical activity

- Walk 30-40 minutes a day;
- Therapeutic gymnastics.

Avoiding bad habits

- Quitting smoking;
- Alcohol restriction.

Prevention of heart disease

1. Regular control of blood pressure.
2. Checking the amount of cholesterol in the blood.
3. Diabetes control.
4. Eating right.
5. Regular physical activity.
6. Reduce excess weight.
7. Stress management.

Conclusion

Effective treatment of heart disease is based on an integrated combination of early diagnosis, medications, interventional procedures, and rehabilitation. In particular, eliminating risk factors and maintaining a healthy lifestyle are the most important measures in preventing cardiovascular disease. It is necessary to consult a cardiologist if any complaints in the heart area arise.